

**DETERMINATION OF THE EFFECTIVE POTENTIAL OF AN
EXCITON IN NANOWIRES BY A COMPUTER METHOD OF PIECEWISE
POLYNOMIAL CALCULATION**

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For a model system of an infinitely long cylindrical nanowire, the effective Coulomb interaction potential between an electron and a hole is determined using a computer method of piecewise polynomial calculation as a function of the distance between the electron and hole. It is shown how the effective Coulomb potential changes with a change in the distance between an electron and a hole for the ground state, in the first and second excited states. In the adiabatic approximation, "exact" numerical results of the effective exciton potential for the lowest three exciton energy levels are obtained, which correspond to simple analytical expressions.

Key words : model, exciton, nanowire , piecewise polynomial method, electron, hole, quantum dot, quantum well, effective potential.

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Coulomb interaction potential between electron and cavity for model systems of infinitely long cylindrical nanowires as a function of distance between electron and cavity was determined by piece-polynomial computer calculation method. In the adiabatic approximation, "exact" numerical results of the effective exciton potential were obtained for the three lowest energy levels of the exciton.

Key words: model, exciton, nanowire, piece-polynomial method, electron, hole, quantum dot, quantum coil, effective potential.

1. Introduction

The study of exciton states in low-dimensional systems (quantum wells, quantum wires, quantum dots and superlattices) occupies one of the central places in condensed matter physics. This is due to the increased practical importance of such systems for microelectronic technologies and the internal logic of the development of physical research. The optical and photoelectric properties of low-dimensional structures turn out to be quite nontrivial and open up quite attractive prospects for applications. For example, it seems quite attractive to create high-speed microelectronic elements based on them, which have significant advantages over those that currently exist. Currently, new types of luminescent screens [1], solar batteries [2], various types of photodetectors [3], and photomultipliers [4] are being actively developed. Exciton states are of interest because they play a significant role in kinetic phenomena - luminescence, light absorption, generation of laser radiation, photoconductivity,

thermal conductivity and chemisorption, various phenomena, with nonequilibrium current carriers.

In [5], an analysis of the influence of the motion of a Wannier-Mott exciton in semiconductors with a superlattice formed by heterojunctions on its binding energy and wave function is presented, in [6] a comparative study of the influence of the type of localizing potential on the binding energy of a biexciton in spherically symmetric quantum dots AB is presented, in [7] aggregation clusters of quantum dots (QDs) on a highly ordered pyrolytic graphite substrate are studied using atomic force microscopy and scanning tunneling microscopy, [8] considered excitons in semiconductor nanostructures as low-dimensional systems, [9] theoretically studied exciton effects on the optical properties of one-dimensional (1D) semiconductors, [10] calculated the main exciton energies and the energies of excited states for a model system of an infinitely long cylindrical wire, and [11] carried out experiments on two-photon absorption and magnetoluminescence, where the main parameters of quasi-one-dimensional excitons were determined. ions, the elementary properties of one-dimensional (1D) excitons in GaAs quantum wires were considered in [12], the Raman scattering spectra of ZnO nanowires and the ZnTe/ZnO core-shell under conditions of nonresonant and resonant excitations by Ar⁺ and He-Cd lasers were measured in [13], and the interband absorption coefficient of a weak electromagnetic wave in quantum wires in a transverse magnetic field was calculated in [14]. field and in the field of intense laser radiation, in [15] the reflection and photoluminescence spectra with quantum wells and thick layers were studied depending on the temperature, intensity, and wavelength of excitation, where the features of the energy spectrum of electrons and holes and their density of states, the formation of exciton states, an increase in the oscillator strength, binding energy, and stabilization of excitons in size-quantized semiconductor wires were studied theoretically and experimentally.

In this work, the effective potential of a one-dimensional (1D) exciton in cylindrical nanowires is determined using a computer method of piecewise polynomial calculation.

2. Model of the effective potential of the 1 D exciton

In the effective mass approximation, the exciton Hamiltonian in a cylindrical wire has the form

$$H = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \vec{\nabla}_e^2 + V_e(\vec{\rho}_e) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h} \vec{\nabla}_h^2 + V_h(\vec{\rho}_h) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z_e^2} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z_h^2} - \frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{e^2}{\sqrt{\rho_e^2 + \rho_h^2 - 2\rho_e\rho_h \cos(\varphi_e - \varphi_h) + (z_e - z_h)^2}}, \quad (1)$$

Where $m_{e(h)}$ is the effective mass of the electron (hole), e is the charge of the electron, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the wire material.

z axis) and movement in the perpendicular plane (0 XY). Then Hamiltonian (1) can be rewritten as

$$H = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \vec{\nabla}_e^2 + V_e(\vec{\rho}_e) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h} \vec{\nabla}_h^2 + V_h(\vec{\rho}_h) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Z^2} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{e^2}{\sqrt{\rho_e^2 + \rho_h^2 - 2\rho_e\rho_h \cos(\varphi_e - \varphi_h) + z^2}} \quad (2)$$

where $Z = (m_e z_e + m_h z_h)/M$ is the coordinate of the translational motion of the center of mass of the exciton, $z = z_e - z_h$ is the coordinate of the relative motion of the electron and hole, $M = m_e + m_h$ is the effective mass of the exciton, $\mu = (m_e m_h)/M$ is the reduced mass of the electron and hole.

We represent the exciton wave function in the form

$$\Psi(\rho_e, \varphi_e, \rho_h, \varphi_h, z, Z) = e^{i\mathcal{K}Z} \phi(z) \psi(\rho_e, \varphi_e) \psi(\rho_h, \varphi_h). \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{K} is the wave vector characterizing the translational motion of the center-of-mass of the exciton. The function $\psi(\rho, \varphi)$ is the solution to the following equation

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \vec{\nabla}^2 + V(\vec{\rho}) \right] \psi(\rho, \varphi) = E \psi(\rho, \varphi). \quad (4)$$

Multiply (3) by $e^{-i\mathcal{K}Z} \psi^*(\rho_e, \varphi_e) \psi^*(\rho_h, \varphi_h)$ the left and by the $e^{i\mathcal{K}Z} \psi(\rho_e, \varphi_e) \psi(\rho_h, \varphi_h)$ right and integrate over the coordinates $\rho_e, \varphi_e, \rho_h, \varphi_h, Z$. Then we obtain the 1D Schrödinger equation for the coordinate of the relative motion of the exciton

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \nabla_z^2 + V_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(z) \right) \phi(z) = E' \phi(z), \quad (5)$$

$$V_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(z) = -\frac{e^2}{\epsilon} \int_0^R \rho_e d\rho_e \int_0^R \rho_h d\rho_h \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_e \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_h \times \\ \times \frac{|\psi_{n,l}(\rho_e, \varphi_e)|^2 |\psi_{n,l}(\rho_h, \varphi_h)|^2}{\sqrt{\rho_e^2 + \rho_h^2 - 2\rho_e \rho_h \cos(\varphi_e - \varphi_h) + z^2}}, \quad (6)$$

$$E' = E_{\text{tot}} - E_g - \frac{\hbar^2 \beta_{n_e, l_e}^2}{2m_e R^2} - \frac{\hbar^2 \beta_{n_h, l_h}^2}{2m_h R^2} - \frac{\hbar^2 \mathcal{K}^2}{2M}, \quad (7)$$

E_g is the band gap of the wire material, $\beta_{n,l}$ are the zeros of the Bessel function of the first kind $J_l(x)$ of the n th order for a given l , R is the cross-sectional diameter of the cylindrical wire.

Taking into account the spherical symmetry of the Coulomb interaction, we perform integrations over φ_e and φ_h , and also passing to dimensionless variables $u = \rho_e/R$, $v = \rho_h/R$ we get

$$V_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(\tilde{z})/E_0 = -8/\pi \int_0^1 u dv |\psi_{n,l}(v)|^2 \int_0^1 u du \frac{|\psi_{n,l}(u)|^2}{\sqrt{(v+u)^2 + \tilde{z}^2}} K\left(\frac{2\sqrt{uv}}{\sqrt{(v+u)^2 + \tilde{z}^2}}\right), \quad (7)$$

$$\psi_{n,l}(x) = [J_{l+1}(\beta_{n,l})]^{-1} J_l(\beta_{n,l}x), \quad E_0 = e^2/\epsilon R, \quad \tilde{z} = z/R, \quad (8)$$

$K(x)$ is an elliptic integral of the first kind.

3. Numerical calculation of the effective exciton potential

To calculate (7), we use the expression of the elliptic integral in terms of the polynomial [16]

$$K(m) = \sum_{i=0}^4 a_i m_1^i + \sum_{i=0}^4 b_i m_1^i \ln \frac{1}{m_1} \equiv \mathbb{A}(m_1) + \mathbb{B}(m_1) \ln(1/m_1), \quad (9)$$

Where $m_1 = 1 - m$

Taking into account (9), we rewrite (7) in the following form

$$\tilde{V}_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(\tilde{z}) = -(2/\pi) \int_0^1 u dv |\psi_{n,l}(v)|^2 I_1(v, \tilde{z}), \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{V}_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(\tilde{z}) = V_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(\tilde{z})/E_0$,

$$I_1(v, \tilde{z}) = 4 \int_0^1 u du \frac{|\psi_{n,l}(u)|^2}{\sqrt{(v+u)^2 + \tilde{z}^2}} [\mathbb{A}(m_1) + \mathbb{B}(m_1) \ln(1/m_1)]. \quad (\text{eleven})$$

To achieve good convergence, we use the logarithmic "heavy" method and consider the integral of the following form:

$$I(v, z) = \int_0^1 du F(u, v, z) \ln \left[\frac{(v-u)^2 + z^2}{(v+u)^2 + z^2} \right]. \quad (12)$$

In what follows, we use transformations in the form:

$$I(v, z) = \sum_{i=0}^{s-1} \int_0^h dx F(x + ih, v, z) \ln \left[\frac{(x-(v-ih))^2 + z^2}{(x+(v+ih))^2 + z^2} \right], \quad (13)$$

where h is the length of the step, s is the total number of steps. If $F(x + ih)$ we replace by $F_i + (F_{i+1} - F_i)(x/h)$, then we rewrite (13) in the form

$$I(v, z) = \sum_{i=0}^{s-1} F_i A_i(v, z) + (F_{i+1} - F_i) C_i(v, z). \quad (14)$$

To solve the problem, it is necessary to determine the coefficients A_i and C_i , which have the form:

$$A_i(v, z) = \int_0^h dx \ln \left[\frac{(x-(v-ih))^2 + z^2}{(x+(v+ih))^2 + z^2} \right]; \quad C_i(v, z) = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^h x dx \ln \left[\frac{(x-(v-ih))^2 + z^2}{(x+(v+ih))^2 + z^2} \right]. \quad (15)$$

These integrals are calculated analytically [17] and lead to the following results:

$$A_i(v, z) = a(h - (v - hi)) - a(h + (v + hi)), \quad (16)$$

$$C_i(v, z) = h^{-1} [c(h - (v - hi)) - c(h + (v + hi))] - 2v, \quad (17)$$

where $a(y) = H_1(y) + H_1(h - y) + 2z[\arctan(y/z) + \arctan((h - y)/z)]$,

$$c(y) = \frac{1}{2} (y(2h - y) + z^2) G_1(y) + \frac{1}{2} ((h - y)^2 - z^2) G_1(h - y) 2z(h - y) \times \\ \times [\arctan(y/z) + \arctan((h - y)/z)],$$

$$H_1(y) = y \ln(y^2 + z^2), \quad G_1(y) = \ln(y^2 + z^2).$$

Taking into account these mathematical operations, we rewrite I_1 from (11) in the following form:

$$I_1(v, \tilde{z}) = \sum_{i=0}^{s-1} \int_0^h dx F(x + hi) [A(m_1) + B(m_1) \ln(1/m_1)] = \\ = \sum_{i=0}^{s-1} [F_i h A(m_1) + F_i (A_i + C_{i-1} - C_i) B(m_1)] + \\ + F_s \frac{h}{2} A(m_1) + F_s C_{s-1} B(m_1), \quad F_i \equiv F(hi) = \frac{4hi |\psi_{n,1}(hi)|^2}{\sqrt{(v+hi)^2 + \tilde{z}}}. \quad (18)$$

At the last stage of solving the problem, it is necessary to calculate the integral over v . For this, we use the result (18). Then for the effective potential we finally obtain the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{V}_{\text{eff}}^{n,l}(\tilde{z}) = & -\frac{2}{\pi} \left\{ h \int_{j=1}^{s-1} h_j |\psi_{n,l}(h_j)|^2 \left[[S_1(h_j)h + T(h_j) \frac{h}{2} \mathbb{A}(m_1)] - \right. \right. \\ & - [S_2(h_j) + T(h_j)C_{s-1} \mathbb{B}(m_1)] \left. \right] + \frac{h}{2} h_s |\psi_{n,l}(h_s)|^2 \left[[S_1(h_s)h + T(h_s) \frac{h}{2} \mathbb{A}(m_1)] - \right. \\ & \left. \left. - [S_2(h_s) + T(h_s)C_{s-1} \mathbb{B}(m_1)] \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{where } S_1(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} \frac{4hi |\psi_{n,l}(hi)|^2}{\sqrt{(x+hi)^2 + \tilde{z}}} \mathbb{A}(m_1), \quad T(x) = \frac{4sh |\psi_{n,l}(sh)|^2}{\sqrt{(x+sh)^2 + \tilde{z}}},$$

$$S_2(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} \frac{4hi |\psi_{n,l}(hi)|^2}{\sqrt{(x+hi)^2 + \tilde{z}}} (A_i + C_{i-1} - C_i) \mathbb{B}(m_1).$$

4. The discussion of the results

Figure 1 shows the results of numerical calculations of the effective exciton potential. It is shown how the effective Coulomb potential changes with a change in the distance between an electron and a hole for the ground state, i.e. $\psi \rightarrow \psi_{0,0}$, ($V^{0,0}$) in both the first and second excited states, i.e. $\psi \rightarrow \psi_{0,1}$ ($V^{0,1}$) and $\psi \rightarrow \psi_{0,2}$ ($V^{0,2}$) respectively.

Fig.1. a) Effective exciton interaction potential as a function of the distance z between the electron and hole for three different states of the electron and hole (solid

curve: $n_e = l_e = 0$ and $n_h = l_h = 0$ for a hole; dotted curve: $l_e = l_h = 1$ and $n_e = n_h = 0$; dotted curve: $l_e = l_h = 2$ and $n_e = n_h = 0$). The usual Coulomb potential, $1/z$, is also plotted (dashed-dotted curve) for comparison. b) effective potential for different sets of electron and hole quantum numbers.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, when the distance between an electron and a hole is about $1.75 R$, the effective potential passes to the one-dimensional Coulomb interaction potential, for which there is an analytical solution to the exciton Schrödinger equation.

Conclusion _

Thus, the effective Coulomb interaction potential of an electron and a hole in a cylindrical nanowire has been numerically calculated using the computer method of piecewise polynomial calculation. The effective potential is numerically calculated for three different states of the electron and hole as a function of the distance between the electron and hole. We were able to present "exact" numerical results. To reduce the amount of computing time for future calculations, these results will be used to propose various analytical approximations. Therefore, when solving certain problems for large z it suffices to use the one-dimensional Coulomb potential, for example, to determine the exciton binding energy.

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